

MORPHOMETRIC ANALYSIS OF DHADHAR RIVER BASIN, GUJARAT

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Abstract

The development of morphometric techniques was a major advance in the quantitative description of the geometry of the drainage basins and its network which helps in characterizing the drainage network, comparing the characteristic of several drainage networks and examining the effect of variables such as lithology, rock structure, rainfall etc. Morphometric analysis and their relative parameters have been quantitatively carried out for the Dhadhar basin, Gujarat, India. The quantitative analysis of the morphometric characteristics of the basin include Stream density, Stream order, Drainage density, Average stream slope, Compactness coefficient, Circulatory ratio, Elongation ratio, Form factor. The forgoing analysis clearly indicates some relations among the various attributes of the morphometric aspects of the basin and helps to understand their role in sculpturing the surface of the region. This study would help the local people to utilize the resources for sustainable development of the basin area.

Key Words: Drainage Network, Stream density, Stream order, Drainage density, Average stream slope, Compactness coefficient, Circulatory ratio, Elongation ratio, Form factor

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Introduction

The optimal and sustainable development of the resources is a prerequisite so that it is assessed rationally to avoid any future problems regarding its qualitative and quantitative availability. Gujarat being a state with moderate to low rainfall, it is very essential to carry out the morphometric analysis of the rivers in order to plan for utilization of water resources. There are many rivers flowing in the state, however not all the rivers are perennial. The present study has been carried out for the river Dhadhar.

About the Study Area

The Dhadhar River is one of the west flowing rivers in Gujarat state . It lies between east longitude $72^{\circ} 30'$ and $73^{\circ} 45'$ and North latitude $21^{\circ} 45'$ and $22^{\circ} 45'$. It originates from the Pavagadh Hills of Gujarat state and flows through Vadodara and Bharuch districts. The river Dhadhar has four tributaries namely Vishwamitri, Jambuo,Surya,Deo. The river Dhadhar after flowing 87 km receives Vishwamitri tributary from right bank at Pingalwada village 500 m upstream of Gauge and Discharge site. After flowing another 55 km it falls in to the Gulf of Khambhat. The total length of the river from its source to outfall in the Gulf of Khambhat is about 142 km. It has a catchment area of 3423 Sq. km.

The major rock types in the upland, central and lower part of the Dhadhar basin are proto-quartzite, sandy phyllite, dolomitic limestone and deep syncline and Cambay graben respectively.

The climate of the basin is semi-arid in nature. It is characterised by general aridity but receives rain from the month of June to September. 93% of the annual rainfall occurs during this period. The maximum, minimum and average rainfall in the basin is 1971mm, 226.06mm and 986mm respectively. Figure 1 shows the catchment plan of the river Dhadhar.

Figure 1 : The catchment area of the Dhadhar basin

Analysis and Discussion

The study is primarily based on published and derived data. Images from SRTM data V3 using WGS 84 at 90 m resolution (<http://srtm.csi.cgiar.org>) have been downloaded and processed for developing the number of streams and sub-basins and morphometric study of the smaller streams of the Dhadhar catchment. The number of sub-basins obtained is thirty two.

The quantitative analysis of the morphometric characteristics – Stream density, Stream order, Drainage density, Average stream slope, Compactness coefficient, Circulatory ratio, Elongation ratio, Form factor – measured and calculated for Dhadhar basin with the help of the images obtained is shown in Table 1.

Table 1 : Morphometric Parameters of Dhadhar basin

Sub basin	Area in m²	Length in m	Perimeter in m	Drainage density in km/km²	Average stream slope	Form factor	Compactness coefficient	Elongation Ratio	Circulatory Ratio
1	260143528.1	47764.98	128059.43	0.184	18.18	0.11	2.24	0.38	0.20
2	170698887.3	43147.53	108600.32	0.253	20.12	0.09	2.35	0.34	0.18
3	12523623.6	10470.88	32493.61	0.836	82.91	0.11	2.59	0.38	0.15
4	46046521.6	13134.73	54856.14	0.285	66.10	0.27	2.28	0.58	0.19
5	90242214.4	27033.03	86608.45	0.300	32.12	0.12	2.57	0.40	0.15
6	558110.8	1492.48	4880.22	2.674	581.70	0.25	1.84	0.56	0.29
7	133063142.4	31179.10	91241.57	0.234	27.84	0.14	2.23	0.42	0.20
8	96576056.0	34440.18	92724.17	0.357	25.21	0.08	2.66	0.32	0.14
9	442486418.0	75371.69	224860.74	0.170	11.52	0.08	3.02	0.31	0.11
10	93990619.8	28590.04	94021.44	0.304	30.37	0.11	2.74	0.38	0.13

11	12343310.8	9170.88	29466.64	0.743	94.67	0.15	2.37	0.43	0.18
12	171603312.8	36295.28	105635.13	0.212	23.92	0.13	2.28	0.41	0.19
13	3525161.1	4381.29	14640.66	1.243	198.16	0.18	2.20	0.48	0.21
14	49647051.5	21527.12	74315.24	0.434	40.33	0.11	2.98	0.37	0.11
15	304137919.5	45933.65	137263.89	0.151	18.90	0.14	2.22	0.43	0.20
16	2296363.4	3093.51	10439.96	1.347	280.65	0.24	1.94	0.55	0.26
17	166395233.3	43587.04	134731.12	0.262	19.92	0.09	2.95	0.33	0.12
18	87377246.0	24063.25	84508.10	0.275	36.08	0.15	2.55	0.44	0.15
19	5198539.2	5328.39	18470.70	1.025	162.93	0.18	2.29	0.48	0.19
20	88488697.3	29131.93	104893.83	0.329	29.80	0.10	3.15	0.36	0.10
21	69867833.2	21118.91	77465.76	0.302	41.11	0.16	2.62	0.45	0.15
22	107489267.7	30825.75	83396.15	0.287	28.16	0.11	2.27	0.38	0.19
23	282702650.7	65526.71	200892.07	0.232	13.25	0.07	3.37	0.29	0.09

24	86355473.9	35200.74	111318.42	0.408	24.66	0.07	3.38	0.30	0.09
25	280776453.1	43221.79	146777.23	0.154	20.09	0.15	2.47	0.44	0.16
26	6446417.7	6575.58	16370.36	1.020	132.03	0.15	1.82	0.44	0.30
27	723158.9	2071.84	5930.39	2.865	419.04	0.17	1.97	0.46	0.26
28	86353566.0	21774.29	89944.30	0.252	39.87	0.18	2.73	0.48	0.13
29	196368165.4	39829.28	134113.37	0.203	21.80	0.12	2.70	0.40	0.14
30	72809124.3	22004.04	93094.82	0.302	39.46	0.15	3.08	0.44	0.11
31	78575314.8	20486.32	76724.46	0.261	42.38	0.19	2.44	0.49	0.17
32	92437450.1	24408.16	84940.53	0.264	35.57	0.16	2.49	0.44	0.16

Linear aspects of the channel system are Stream order and Stream length. The Dhadhar basin shows a near perfect correlation with the plots falling very near regression line and even at the sub-basib level the correlation satisfies the Horton's law. Figure 2 shows the drainage pattern and their order identified for the Dhadhar basin. The stream orders and stream lengths have been worked out as shown in table 2 and comparative plots for stream order versus stream length as well as for stream order versus stream number has been plotted in Figure 3.

Figure 2 :Drainage pattern and their order identified from the study area

Table 2. Details of Stream order and Stream Length for Dhadhar basin

Stream order	Stream number	Stream length in kms
1	555	1072.43
2	502	575.727
3	399	265.608
4	128	218.55
5	41	78.3811

Figure. 2 : Geometric relation between Stream orders, Stream length and Stream numbers

Calculation of Parameters

Basin Length : The length of Dhadhar basin is 142 Km while the lengths of sub-basins are shown in table 1.

Form factor (Ff) : The form factor of the Dhadhar basin is 0.14 while the form factor of sub-basins are shown in table 1. The formula used for find the form factor is $Ff = A/L_b^2$ Where A = Area of sub-basin and L_b = axial length of the basin

Elongation ratio (Er) : The elongation ratio of the Dhadhar basin is 0.42 while the elongation ratio of sub-basins are shown in table 1. Are extremely elongated nature. The elongation ratio is related to rock types in the basin and also to the physiography and slope. The formula used for find the elongation ratio is $Er = 2R/L_b$ Where $R = \sqrt{A/\pi}$ and A = Area of sub-basin

Circularity ratio (Cr) : The circularity ratio of the Dhadhar basin is 0.17 while the circularity ratio of sub-basins are shown in table 1. The formula used for find the circularity ratio is $Cr = (4*\pi*A) / (P^2)$ where A = Area of sub-basin and P = Perimeter of sub-basin

Average stream slope (Avg. S): The average stream slope of the Dhadhar basin is 83.09 while the average stream slope of sub-basins are shown in table 1

Compectness coefficient (Cc) : The compectness coefficient of the Dhadhar basin is 2.52 while the compectness coefficient of sub-basins are shown in table 1

Drainage density (Dd) : The drainage density of the Dhadhar basin is $0.52\text{km}/\text{km}^2$ while the drainage density of sub-basins are shown in table 1. The formula to find drainage density is $Dd = L_s/A$ where L = the total length of streams within a basin and A = the area of the basin. A high value of the drainage density would indicate a relatively high density of streams and thus a rapid storm response.

Stream Order (Nu)

In the drainage basin analysis the first step is to determine the stream orders. In the present study, the channel segment of the drainage basin has been ranked according to Strahler's stream ordering system. According to Strahler (1964), the smallest fingertip tributaries are designated as order 1. Where two first order channels join, a channel segment of order 2 is formed; where two of order 2 join, a segment of order 3 is formed; and so forth. The trunk stream through which all discharge of water and sediment passes is therefore the stream segment of highest order. The study area is a 5 th order drainage basin

Bifurcation Ratio (Rb)

The term bifurcation ratio (Rb) is used to express the ratio of the number of streams of any given order to the number of streams in next higher order (Schumn, 1956).

The linear aspects of the drainage network for Dhadhar basin have been worked out and tabulated in table 3. In the table L_u indicates the total stream length of all orders while N_u indicates the total no. of streams of all orders. The same have been used to work out the Bifurcation ration Rb

Table 3: Linear aspects of the drainage network of the study area

Stream order u	Number of Streams Nu	Total length of streams in km Lu	Log Nu	Log Lu	Bifurcation ratio
1	555	1072.43	2.74	3.03	
					1.11
2	502	575.73	2.7	2.76	
					1.26
3	399	265.61	2.6	2.42	
					3.11
4	128	218.55	2.10	2.34	
					3.12
5	41	78.38	1.61	1.89	

Conclusions :

The quantitative analysis of morphometric parameters is found to be of immense utility in river basin evaluation, watershed prioritization for soil and water conservation, and natural resources management at micro level. The morphometric analysis carried out in the lower Dhadhar river basin shows that the basin is having low relief of the terrain and elongated in shape. Drainage network of the basin exhibits as mainly dendritic type which indicates the homogeneity in texture and lack of structural control. In some parts of the basin, the dipping and jointing of the topography reveals parallel and radial pattern. The linear pattern of the graphical representation indicates the weathering erosional characteristics of the area under study. The morphometric parameters evaluated using GIS helped us to understand various terrain parameters such as nature of the bedrock, infiltration capacity, runoff, etc. Similar studies in conjunction with high resolution satellite data help in better understanding the landforms and their processes and drainage pattern demarcations for basin area planning and management.

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